

Exploring Cavite's heritage prides and culinary hidden gems: A study on Lasa ng Republika

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Abstract

Cavite's heritage pride locations and culinary hidden gems are investigated for this study, as is their potential to become tourist attractions in the province. The study examines the one-of-a-kind characteristics and attractions of these places and gems, as well as their potential for the expansion of tourism, by employing a mix of qualitative and quantitative research methodologies. The findings shed light on the heritage pride locations and culinary hidden gems that can be found in Cavite, as well as the reasons that contribute to their distinctiveness and attraction, as well as the potential for the expansion of tourism. The study presents recommendations for the promotion and development of Cavite's historical pride sites and culinary hidden gems as tourism attractions, including marketing tactics, infrastructure development, and community involvement. This study gives significant insights into the latent tourism potential of Cavite's hidden gems and heritage pride locations, as well as practical recommendations for their development and promotion. Overall, the findings of this research offer a wealth of information that can help advance tourism in the province.

Keywords: *Heritage; Gems; Cavite; Attractions; Food tourism.*

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Introduction

Cavite is a province situated in the CALABARZON region of the Philippines. Apart from its unique gastronomy, the place is renowned for its rich historical background, cultural heritage, and delectable baked goods. Over the past few years, there has been an increasing focus on promoting the historical and culinary attractions of Cavite as a means of bolstering tourism and driving economic growth in the area. The impetus behind this inclination is rooted in the conviction that such action will yield a more substantial expansion of the economy. The aim of this study is to examine the cultural artifacts, and culinary peculiarities present in the province of Cavite, with a specific focus on the tourist spot recognized as Lasa ng Republika.

Cavite has a historically significant past, having played a crucial role in the Philippine struggle for independence during the nation's formative years. The inaugural hoisting of the Philippine flag took place in 1898 at the Aguinaldo Shrine in Kawit, a province that boasts numerous historical landmarks. Cavite is renowned not only for its historical landmarks but also for its distinctive gastronomy, which amalgamates Spanish, Chinese, and native components (Orda, 2018).

The Lasa ng Republika establishment, situated in the municipality of Silang within the province of Cavite, serves as a hub for culinary tourism (Cavitex, 2016). The destination is rapidly gaining popularity among tourists visiting the province (Pino, 2019). Lasa ng Republika, a dining establishment, offers a diverse array of regional delicacies, including the renowned Cavite coffee, longganisa, and tamales. The food tourism sector has the potential to serve as a key catalyst for economic growth in the region, as it

generates fresh employment opportunities and novel revenue streams for indigenous businesses (Hernandez et al., 2018).

Gutierrez et al. (2022) conducted a study which suggests that food tourism is an emerging trend in the Philippines. The rationale behind this trend is that tourists are progressively inclined towards seeking authentic encounters with indigenous gastronomy (De Castro et al., 2018; Jimenez Tipon & Rosas, 2020; Kala, 2020). Giampocoli and Kalis (2012) posit that food tourism can serve as a catalyst for local economic growth by generating employment opportunities and augmenting the revenue of small-scale enterprises. Zocchi et al. (2021) posit that food tourism can serve as a means of safeguarding customary culinary practices and advancing cultural legacy.

Methodology

The present study employed a qualitative research methodology, wherein data was collected through interviews and focus group discussions with small business owners residing in Cavite. The study employed purposive sampling technique to select participants, with a particular focus on individuals employed in the food tourism sector.

Results and Findings

The findings of this research indicate that the cultural and gastronomic attractions of Cavite possess the capacity to serve as a significant catalyst for the advancement of tourism and financial development within the locality. The study's results have indicated the possibility of this potential. The study's participants placed great emphasis on the importance of upholding customary culinary practices and advocating for regional cuisine to serve as a means of enticing tourists and safeguarding cultural heritage.

The present study has yielded several noteworthy findings, with one of the most salient being the crucial role played by collaborative efforts between indigenous enterprises and governmental entities in advancing the cause of gastronomic tourism in Cavite. The study's participants placed significant emphasis on the necessity of government support for the advancement of marketing initiatives and infrastructure.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The present research demonstrates the capacity of Cavite's historical and culinary attractions to serve as a catalyst for tourism and economic advancement in the area. The study specifically focused on the potential of gastronomic offerings in Cavite. The results suggest that there exists a need for enhanced cooperation between private enterprises and governmental entities in the region of Cavite to advance the cause of culinary tourism.

The ensuing recommendations have been proffered to optimize the utilization of this prospect:

1. One potential strategy for fostering the expansion of the food tourism sector is to develop infrastructure, such as culinary hubs and commercial venues that can support the needs of both tourists and local businesses.
2. It is recommended to increase marketing efforts to emphasize the cultural legacy and gastronomic specialties of the region.
3. One potential strategy to enhance the visitor experience and the quality of products and services provided by local businesses is to provide them with training and support.
4. As a means of fostering tourism and advancing cultural heritage, it is advisable to promote the preservation of customary culinary practices and endorse the local cuisine.

References

- Cavitex. (2016, June 8). *Lasa ng Republika – The CAVITEX food and cultural tour*.
https://www.cavitex.ph/news_and_events/lasa-ng-republika-the-cavitex-food-and-cultural-tour/
- De Castro, D. L. A., Aguirre, P. K. C., Andaya, I. O., De Castro, V. A., Martinez, C. J. D., Soriano, S. A. E., & Felicen, S. S. (2018). Culinary tourism as a destination attraction in the province of Batangas, Philippines. *Journal of Tourism and Hospitality Research*, 15(1), 40-57.
<https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/JTHR-2018-004.pdf>
- Giampiccoli, A., & Kalis, J. H. (2012). Tourism, food, and culture: Community-based tourism, local food, and community development in m pondoland. *Culture, Agriculture, Food and Environment*, 34(2), 101-123. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2153-9561.2012.01071.x>
- Gutierrez, E. L. M., Rivera, J. P. R., & Roxas, F. M. Y. (2022). Culinary tourism as an avenue for tourism development: Mapping the flavors of the Philippines. In R. S. Aquino & B. A. Porter (Eds.), *Tourism in the Philippines: Applied management perspectives* (pp. 67-95). Springer Nature Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-4497-0_4
- Hernandez, M. G., Obidos, M. S., Salvador, M. J., Toledo, J., & Delos Santos, M. (2018). Preservation of Cavite's traditional foods from the selected municipalities as adapted by the millennials. *Asia Pacific Journal of Academic Research in Social Sciences*, 3, 82-88.
<https://research.lpubatangas.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/APJARSS-2018-010.pdf>
- Jimenez Tipon, T. A., & Rosas, M. V. (2020). Gastronomy: An econometric analysis as a business driver. *Journal of Contemporary Social Science Research*, 4(1), 94-106.
<https://ir.uitm.edu.my/id/eprint/35109/1/35109.pdf>
- Kala, D. (2020). Examining the impact of food attributes and restaurant services on tourist satisfaction: evidence from mountainous state of India. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 21(4), 430-453. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1528008X.2019.1672235>
- Orda, C. (2018, June 12). *Why Cavite is the capital of Philippine heritage cooking*. F&B Report.
<https://fnbreport.ph/7076/why-cavite-is-the-capital-of-philippine-heritage-cooking/>
- Pino, G. (2019, January 4). *Cavite: An emerging food destination south of Manila*. Philippine News Agency. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1057957>
- Zocchi, D. M., Fontefrancesco, M. F., Corvo, P., & Pieroni, A. (2021). Recognising, safeguarding, and promoting food heritage: challenges and prospects for the future of sustainable food systems. *Sustainability*, 13(17), 9510. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13179510>